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MODERN ASPECTS IN THE BIOMEDICAL ETHICS OF THE PHYSICIAN WHEN STUDYING THE DISCIPLINE "FUNDAMENTALS OF BIOETHICS AND BIOSAFETY"

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Abstract

The article reveals the expediency of studying the discipline "Fundamentals of Bioethics and Biosafety" by medical students, namely the need to disclose to them modern aspects of biomedical ethics, problematic issues related to further clinical practice and overcoming barriers to establishing doctor-patient relationship. The article defines the need for future physicians to comply with the principles of biomedical ethics of a medical practitioners in order to facilitate their further clinical practice and increase competitiveness on the domestic and international labor markets.

Keywords: educational process, fundamentals of bioethics and biosafety, physician's ethics.

Since ancient times, the physician's profession has been special, filled with faith and hope, despair and suffering, pain or, on the contrary, health and well-being. It remains unchanged that the most gifted, highly intelligent and hardworking students become doctors, whose most important aspiration is self-improvement for further constant work in the field of medicine [1]. However, in connection with a large number of reforms in all fields of science, socio-economic changes in the world, significant changes have also occurred in medicine: modern medical technologies, new methods and types of treatment have appeared, the attitude towards medical workers has changed, the awareness of patients and the responsibility of doctors have increased, etc. [2]. For that reason, at the Bukovinian State Medical University the subject "Fundamentals of Bioethics and Biosafety" is mandatory for study, such allows to reveal the potential of medical students, consolidate their knowledge, facilitate and harmonize their further clinical practice, improve relations with colleagues, as well as with patients and their families, and, the main thing, is to tune in to health-preserving activity. Modern medicine presents a whole range of unresolved controversial bioethical issues to the future medical specialist, which are sometimes difficult for an experienced physician to deal with [3]. Therefore, in the "Fundamentals of Bioethics and Biosafety" classes, teachers of the Department of Pharmacology consider with students the bioethical aspects of the professional activity of medical workers, the issue of the

relationship between the patient, his family and the medical staff, the responsibility, duties and privileges of the physicians, medical errors in clinical practice, etc. At the same time, special attention is paid to the formation of future medics' communication skills and the ability to establish trusting and friendly relationship with patients, which is a prerequisite of successful pharmacotherapy and further cooperation in the prevention of diseases and adherence to the principles of a healthy lifestyle [4].

A true physician have to devote his life to medicine, i.e. through his whole life carry respect and gratitude to his teachers, work conscientiously and with dignity, protect and strengthen the health of patients – the most valuable thing the doctors deal with, as well as maintain the honor and traditions of the medical profession with his work. In order to meet all these requirements, medics go through a rather long period of training, because insufficient competence is the cause of ineffective treatment and death of patients. However, the task of future specialists is not only to thoroughly learn the necessary material, but also to learn how to improve, work on themselves, constantly and independently enrich the acquired medical knowledge. Although, having only a high degree of competence, a doctor will not be a full-fledged specialist, because without such virtues as compassion, responsibility, prudence, and the ability to self-sacrifice, he will not be able to make the right decisions, and implement them.

The presence of these qualities is a moral guarantee for patients and a basis for trust and authority.

What does professionalism mean to the Physician? Professionalism is not only a relationship between a physician and a patient, but also a relationship between colleagues and other medical professionals, behavior and a certain life position in society. After all, society grants this profession special privileges, but in return it requires exceptional responsibility and concentration, the ability to use these privileges not for one's own good, but for the good of others.

No matter how knowledgeable a physician is, he can't be an expert in all matters of medicine, so he needs the help of other specialized doctors and qualified medical workers. Coordinated work and close cooperation between medical practitioners is mandatory, only by complementing each other's knowledge and skills, it is possible to reproduce a complex picture of the disease and provide specialized care. As for relations with other medical professionals: nurses, pharmacists, etc., the first place should be a team approach to help the patient, in which the competence of all team members will be given equal attention. But the crucial is, that the ethical issues of the relationship of medical workers have to be instilled to medics yet by their teachers and tutors, since their relations with colleagues and behavior are the role models for future physicians. The Declaration of Geneva affirms: "I will give to my teachers, colleagues, and students the respect and gratitude that is their due". For their part, medical students must adhere to the high standards of ethical behavior required of future physicians. They should help each other, treat each other collegially and take an active part in the social and public life of the university where they study.

In medical practice, regardless of position or experience, some questions are much easier to answer than others. Stopping minor bleeding and suturing a simple wound pose few questions to specialists who are used to performing these procedures. On the other hand, there is great uncertainty or inconsistency in how to communicate with patients in certain, especially critical, situations, how to establish trusting relationship with certain patients, how to treat certain diseases and provide quality palliative care. Thus, ethical issues in medical practice are not all equally difficult. Some of them are quite easy to answer, because there is a clear algorithm regarding the correct actions in a particular situation (e.g., a doctor must always adhere to the principle of confidentiality and medical secrecy in relation to his patients from the point of view of law and biomedical ethics). However, there are much more complex issues, especially those for which no clear course of action has been developed or where all alternatives are flawed (e. g., such as organ and tissue transplantation, stem cell use, in vitro fertilization, use of embryonic tissue for treatment, gene therapy, sex reassignment, the use of transgenic organisms for the purpose of obtaining food products and, finally, animal and human cloning).

Undoubtedly, the status of physician is influenced by many factors, but it differs depending on the country and even within a medical clinic or a certain department

in a hospital. Although, in general, it can be argued that it is getting worse, given a number of problems that have arisen in modern medicine. Many physicians feel that the attitude towards them has changed, that they are no longer as respected as they once were. After all, in many countries, control over health care has clearly passed from physicians to professional managers, who are categorically unwilling or unable to see the real problems of clinical medicine. Along with this, patients who previously fulfilled the physicians' appointments without asking too many questions, relying on the advice of incompetent friends or information on the Internet, now actively discuss with them. Considering such changes, the study of biomedical ethics by medical students is necessary and becomes especially relevant [5].

One of the important levers in the practical activity of a physician is the observance of the principle of confidentiality, which is so thoroughly revealed by the Hippocratic Oath: "What I can see and hear during treatment or even outside of treatment in relation to people's lives, which in no case should be disseminated, I will keep in himself, refraining from such shameful things as talking about it". This principle includes three sources: independence, respect for others, and trust. Independence refers to confidentiality in that the patient's personal information belongs only to him and should not be known to others without his consent. If a patient discloses personal information to a doctor or nurse, or when that information is made public for other reasons, those involved must keep it confidential until the patient gives permission to disclose it. Confidentiality is also important because all patients deserve respect as human beings. And respect for a person is manifested in preserving their privacy. However, the doctor must be very careful to determine what personal information the patient wants to keep secret and what he wants to share with others. For this, the patient should trust the doctor. This trust is based on ethical and legal standards of confidentiality, which medical professionals have to maintain [6].

Unfortunately, reduced work productivity, trying to adjust to limited physical capabilities, coming to terms with thoughts of imminent death, preoccupation with one's own experiences, reluctance to interact with a doctor, and the use of large number of medication are just some of the challenges, that older adults face on a daily basis. In the classes, future physicians learn to provide moral support and sincerely sympathize, because elderly patients with their great experience very easily notice falsehood and insincerity towards them. When solving situational problems in class, medical students understand that the activity of the physician is not formal services, but the ability to be an attentive and benevolent interlocutor, a patient assistant, a balanced adviser. Future physicians should understand that a doctor's disorganization, sloppiness, and lack of interest cause an elderly person to be wary and can become an obstacle in establishing trusting and friendly relationships. The physician have to respect the values and sense of independence of the elderly and find an individual approach to each of them, weighing each of his actions. Therefore, one of the tasks of

teachers when medical students study the discipline "Fundamentals of Bioethics and Biosafety" is the perfect development of their communicative competence, which involves the achievement of understanding with patients [7]. Additionally, it allows the physician to thoroughly find out the social anamnesis of elderly patients, living conditions, family relationships, and most importantly – the presence of bad habits and adherence to the principles of a healthy lifestyle. In the classes, great attention is paid to the role of professional competence among students, because knowledge of gerontological and psychological features of people of this age gives the doctor the opportunity to choose optimal schemes of treatment and prevention of diseases. Doubtless, that the principles of morality, honesty and unconditional devotion must be followed by physician when working with elderly patients. Evidently, that a sense of respect for such patients and interest in their life experience increases trust in physician, affirms his authority as specialist in the eyes of elderly people [8].

It is essential, that teachers should constantly emphasize the need to promote shared decision-making based on a mutual respect and taking into account beliefs, concerns, and expectations of elderly patients to increase compliance and improve treatment outcomes. Therefore, it is doctors who, through their professional activities due to an appropriate psychosocial approach and knowledge of the bioethical aspects of communication with such patients, should ensure the physical, mental and social well-being, and equal opportunities to older people for their participation in all areas of life [9].

Creating a health-preserving environment when teaching future physicians "Fundamentals of Bioethics and Biosafety" is one of the key tasks of this discipline. This requires clear observance of the main principles: humanization of the educational process; consideration of individual characteristics of students; openness, which involves easy interaction; systemicity – interconnection of all components of the health care environment; accessibility, i.e. coverage of all participants in the educational process. Moreover, the attitude of medical students to their own health is the basis of health care, since through the motivation of this attitude, it is possible to carry out value-oriented activities of doctors to preserve and strengthen the health of others [10].

Environmental education of future medical specialists is of great value, characterized not only by theoretical possession of ecological knowledge and skills, but also by a mandatory active environmental protection position. Environmental education is part of the general comprehensive education of the individual and, at the same time, is an independent type of education, because it differs from other types of education in terms of goals and methods of implementing specific tasks. Furthermore, both environmental education and upbringing form a harmoniously developed personality, refining the psycho-emotional and intellectual spheres of medical students, the ability to predict the conse-

quences of their behavior in nature and society, the ability to think logically and make constructive decisions regarding the preservation of the environment. As a result, such competence forms an attitude towards nature as the world of their being and the future existence of their descendants.

Thus, the physician should treat the patient not as a person in general, but as an individual. The humanism of the physician coincides with the social function of medicine and is embodied in moral ideas and feelings. That is manifested in an active, free desire to devote himself to patients and, overcoming difficulties, to use all opportunities for recovery and health protection, without at the same time causing by actions and words additional suffering. The basis of a physician's professional morality is his attitude to the patient and to people's health in general. At the same time, attention has to be focused on the need to strengthen health and prolong the life of an individual and society. Therefore, meeting this need is a professional task and a moral goal of a physician, which requires constant improvement, development and non-traditional approaches in its implementation.

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